

Effectiveness of Reality and Behavior Therapy for the Treatment of Conversion Disorder: A Quasi Experimental Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 10, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: June 11, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Quasi-experimental, Reality Therapy, Behavior therapy, Conversion Disorder, personality disorder, Pharmacological Treatment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8048323</p>	<p><i>Conversion disorder accounting for 12.4 percent of inpatient psychiatric admissions. Unfortunately, there are no proven treatments specifically for conversion disorder. Choice Theory is based on the fact that individuals have control on their internal, external environment and the quality of life of an individual develop and stressor were removed. The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the reality therapy and behavior therapy technique i.e progressive muscle relaxation among female outpatients of conversion disorder. The quasi-experimental study was conducted from Jun 2022 to January 2023. On the sample of 30 female outpatients age 18-35 years diagnosed with conversion disorder. The sample was selected conveniently from three tertiary care hospitals Peshawar. The sample were divided into two groups i.e. Experimental and control group. The SDS, IPDE and BCI were used for both pretesting and post testing period. The reality therapy with behavior therapy technique i.e. progressive muscle relaxation were used for experimental group while pharmacological treatment for control group. At post testing period the independent sample t test of experimental group $M=12.3 \pm 3.4$ and control group $M=12.3, \pm 3.9, t(28).145 p = .88 (< .05)$ and Cohen's $d = .04$ very small effect size at score of SDS. At BCI the control group $M=70, \pm 11.6$, experimental group $M=90, \pm 7.1, t(28) -5.8, p = 000 (< .05)$ with Cohen's $d 2.0$ which shows the BCI were improved after therapeutic intervention. The study concluded significant differences between baseline and endline period of both experimental and control group. Thus it provides evidence reality therapy can be considered as a useful therapy with profounding improvement in the life of conversion patients.</i></p>

Introduction

Sigmund Freud coined the term "hysteria" to describe the bizarre physical symptoms that supplement the conversion condition. Despite the fact that no physiological basis for their existence could be determined, he argued that these symptoms were caused by an unconscious power (Freud, 1962a, 1962b).

In Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5, however, a new category called "functional neurological disorder" has been added for episodes that require to remove apparent stressors (DSM 4th, 2000). Conversion disorder is an unsolved neurological condition or a psychological disorder characterized by the presence of symptoms affecting the patient voluntary behavior that advocate a general medical condition. Somatoform disorder, dissociation disorder, or somatization are all terms used to describe it (Thompson et al., 2012). "Symptoms of conversion disorder are sometimes puzzling and distressing to the patients because it is not within the conscious control of the patient" (Brown et al., 2002). One type of conversion disorder is pseudo-seizures, which are utmost problematic symptom to recognize as of their organic counterpart. Conversion disorders are frequently linked to stressful life experiences, and they can arise when present life stressors trigger childhood trauma (Kroenke & Swindle, 2000). Conversion disorder was treated using hypnosis, relaxation techniques, visualization, and biofeedback (Alper, 1997).

However, the International Classification of Diseases-11 classifies conversion disorder as a dissociative condition. According to a research conducted in Pakistan, conversion disorder is one of the most important psychiatric disorder, accounting for 12.4 percent of inpatient psychiatric admissions (Farooq, 2007). According to another survey, it is Pakistan's fifth most frequent psychiatric condition (Nizami et al., 2005). Female gender, young age, low socio-economic status, joint family, and illiteracy have all been identified as major risk factors for Conversion disorder both in India (Vyas, 1977) and Pakistan (Aamir, Farooq & Jahangir, 2011).

In conversion disorder patients feel difficult to cope with stressful situations, where Cope is described as ways that an individual applies to deal with the outer and/or inner anxieties during a stressful condition (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980).

To treat patients with conversion disorder behavior therapy was formally used by clinical psychologist in late 1950's and in early 1960's (Eysenck, 1959). Behavior therapy defines that all behaviors are learned whether adoptive and maladaptive. Exposure techniques, social services training, modelling, aversion therapy, contingency management, and systematic desensitization are examples of behavior therapy procedures for the treatment of maladaptive behavior change (Campo & Negri, 2000).

Nicholson et al. (2016) Psychosocial stresses were typically recognized in psychological model of Conversion disorder at time of incubation period. After the conversion symptoms started The Life Events Scale and Difficulties Schedule Scale was used to assess 43 motor impairment conversion disorder (CD) patients, 28 depression patients, and 28 healthy controls subjects. The notion of Freudian idea state that in order to escape from the stressor as secondary achievement CD were developed.

Reality therapy model of WDEP (wants, doing, evaluation and planning) is used for improving quality of life of an individual and also develop healthy behavior as a result of good choices. Dr. William Glasser's developed Choice Theory/Reality Therapy. It was first appeared in the 1960s under the name "Reality Therapy," and by the 1980s, it had become associated with "Control Theory." Glasser renamed "Control Theory" to "Choice Theory" in June 1996, (Wubbolding, 2000). Choice Theory is based on the fact that individuals have control on their internal and external environment. On the bases of these reality based choices and control, the quality of life of an individual develop (Bradley, 2004).

Rationale

There is a lack of evidence of the role of reality therapy for the treatment of Conversion disorder in Pakistan. Therefore, this study explores the option of utilization of the reality therapy for the treatment of outpatient's female of conversion disorder in Pakistan. The overall purpose of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of reality therapy with the combination of behavior therapy technique i.e progress muscle relaxation technique for treatment of patients with conversion disorder in the tertiary care hospital of Peshawar, KP.

The results of this study will help in developing effective treatment measures for conversion disorders in our settings and will cause improvement in the quality of life of conversion patients and their respective families. Current study will enable health care providers to make evidence based decisions regarding the treatment of such patients. This study will provide a strong basis for future researchers to conduct further studies on such topics. This study will be shared with the policy makers to make better evidence based decisions which will enable maximum benefits to such patients.

Methods:

Design and Source of Data:

This was a Quasi Experimental Study, with the sample consisting of 30 females (N=30) diagnosed with acute conversion disorder. Sample for both experimental and control group were (n=15), as suggested by authors for quasi experimental study (Cohen et al., 2007 & Gall et al., 1996).

Study Settings and Participants:

The sample was taken from tertiary care hospitals of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Female outpatients diagnosed with conversion disorder with age range of 18-35 years were selected. Inpatients diagnosed with conversion disorder, patients having medical condition, drug addicts, other psychiatric illness and male patients diagnosed with conversion disorder were excluded from the study.

Phase I: Outpatient from the three tertiary care hospitals and clinically diagnosed with conversion disorder (functional neurological symptom disorder) were evaluated by Sheehan Disability Scale, IPDE screening and Brief Cope Inventory .

Phase II. After an initial assessment the sample was divided conveniently into experimental and control groups. With study design of treatment package strategy, Control group received pharmacological treatment only, while Experimental group received psychological interventions i.e reality therapy and behavior therapy (progressive muscle relaxation) with pharmacological treatment. Experimental group of patients received 10-15 sessions in total (3 sessions per week).

Phase III: Post-testing period intended to assess the effectiveness of the treatment interventions. Sheehan Disability Scale and Brief cope were reapplied in both the groups.

Ethical Approval:

Formal ethical approval was taken from Graduate Study Committee (GSC) and Advanced Study Research Board (ASRB). Informed consent were taken from the respondents before initiating the study and confidentiality was retained. All ethical principle was followed throughout the study period.

Outcome Measures:

Semi structure interview were conducted in order to take demographic information of the selected respondents i.e. Age, residence, marital status, employment, socio economic status, mental history of siblings, number of siblings, sexual history, number of children, drug history, number of hospital admissions, onset of episodes, co morbidities with other psychological disorders, pharmacological treatment, duration of medication, age of onset of symptoms, duration of the fits, orientation during the fits, date of intervention of the Reality therapy,

worksheets of the Reality therapy, number of sessions were calculated, Reality worksheets were used to measure improvement or otherwise among the patient, IDPE, SDS, BCI instruments were used for measuring the personality disorders, disability and coping abilities among the patients.

The instruments were the “Sheehan Disability Scale” (SDS) by David Sheehan in 1981 (Sheehan,2008) was developed to give a quick but accurate self-reported assessment of impairment in functioning for patients in psychiatric condition. The scale contains five-items on each of the three domains, that assesses patient’s impairment on family life/home tasks, work/school and social life/leisure activities and are impacted by psychological or health condition. To each question, there are 11 alternative answers on a horizontal line ranging from 0 (not at all), 1–3 (mildly), 4–6 (moderately), 7–9 (markedly), and 10 (very extremely). The Cronbach alpha value range from 0.70 to 0.90 (Coles et al., 2014).

The “International Personality Disorder Examination” (IPDE) screening questionnaire suitable for the assessment of personality disorders both in the DSM, 5th Edition and ICD ,10th edition (IPDE; Loranger, 1999). IPDE is applicable to 18 years and above while some of the researcher utilized it for age 15, consists of 77 items with true and false options. The internal consistency reliability analysis of IPDE consists of criteria for three cluster values; cluster A α ,0.88, cluster B α ,0.93 and for cluster C α , 0.88, cut off points (≥ 3 to ≥ 5) (Gumà et al., 2016).

COPE inventory (Carver, C.S,1989) is multi-dimensional questionnaire design to evaluate numerous coping techniques for stress. It has 28 questions on a four-point Likert scale. (1=I have not done this at all, 2=I have done this a little, 3 I have done this a moderate amount, and 4= I have done this a lot).it contains four subscales i-e. Coping through a **Problem-Focused Approach** (Items 2, 5,7, 10, 14, 23, 25). **Positive Cope Strategies consists of** (Items 12,15,17,18,20,24 and 28). **Avoidant Coping** (Items 1, 4, 6, 9, 11, 13, 16,19,21 and 26) **Religious/Denialcoping** comprised items (3,8,22 and 27) (Dias, Cruz & Fonseca,2012).

Statistical Analysis:

Results were analyzed through SPSS v.25(statistical and social science package). For demographic variable i.e., age, education, socioeconomic status, drug history, psychiatric illness and onset of symptoms etc. frequency, percentages were calculated and graphs prepared. Mean, standard deviation was calculated for the scores of Sheehan disability, Brief cope and IPDE. After calculating the scores, the standard score was calculated through categorical variables. For comparison of Control and Experimental groups through IPDE, BCI and Sheehan disability in both pre-test and post-test the paired t-test and independent sample t-test were utilized when the data was normally distributed, Wilcoxon signed rank test was used for the data not distributed normally. For associations of comorbid variables with other variables chi-square test was used.

Results

Patients characteristics

Demographic characteristics of the respondents N=30 of female conversion patients. There were 2 groups of study i.e. experimental group n=15 (50%) and control group n=15 (50%), in which age range were from 15-20 n= 9 (30%), 21-25 n=10 (33.3%), 26-30 n=2 (6.6%) and 31-35 n=9 (30%) . The education levels were categorizing into primary n= 5(16.7%), secondary n=4(13.3%), higher secondary n=2(6.7%), graduation n=1 (3.3%) and uneducated n=18 (60%). Socioeconomic status was upper class (>10000) n=0(0%), middle class 50000-10000 n=11(36%) and lower class <50000 n=19 (63. 3%).About two- third of the respondents were married. Sibling were categorizing 1-3 n=2 (6.7%),4-6 n=11 (36.7%) and 7-9 n=17 (56.7%). Birth order included 1st born n=7(23.3%), 2nd and middle born n= 17 (56.7%) and last born= 6 (20%).Of the total majority n= 27 (90%) were living in the joint family, whereas n=3 (10%) were living in a nuclear family system. Area of residence of the study patients showed that majority were Peshawar n=19(63.3), followed by Khyber Agency n= 2(6.6%) Swabi n=18 (26.6%) and Kabul n= 1 (3.3%).The physical illness/ co-morbid which were categorize into none n=19(63.3%), hypertension and diabetes n=3(10%), Lymphoma n=2(6.7%), Pancreatic/n=1(3.3%) Stomach Ulcer n=3(10%), Polio n=1(3.3%)and Facial Palsy n=1(3.3%).Number of hospital Admission, no Admission n=19(63.3%), 1 time admitted n=6(20%), 2 time admitted (n=3) 10% and 3 time admitted n=2(6.7%). Comorbid psychological disorder i.e. Anxiety disorder (n=3) 10%, Depressive Disorder (n=24) 80%, Psychotic Disorder (n=1) 3.3% and Nil (n=2) 6.7%. Onset of conversion symptoms started 1-10 days (n=3) 10%, 11-20 days (n=2) 6.7%, one month (n=8) 26%, two months (n=5) 16% and one year (n=12) 40%. Episode include 1st episode (n=2) 6.7%, 2nd episode (n=16) 53% and 3rd episode (n=12) 40%. Sexual history of those patients who are married nil (n=12) 40%, Good (n=15) 50% and Poor (n=3) 10%. There were no drug History of any patients both experimental and control group.

The Pharmacological treatment both experimental and control groups (N=30)the generic name of the list of pharmacological treatment to the patients of conversion disorder. The data shows as Inderal 10mg were the most prevalent prescription combination. The other combination of antidepressants medicine includes fluoxetine 100mg, sensival 25mg, citalopram 10mg, paroxetin30mg/quetiapine 30mg, olanzapine 100mg and citraline 50mg etc. in which cluster B n=2 (6.7%), those who’s score both in cluster A and B n=2 (6.7%), those who falls in B and C n=20 (66.7%) and those who’s fall in A, B and C n=6(20%).

As personality clusters (N=30) shows data of three scales i-e SDS, BCI and ABC personality clusters. Since it has been showed in the data sample is small and it's been needed to choose appropriate statistical tests. So Shapiro-wilk significant value for normality of data were of SDS ($W=.90, p < .05$), BCI ($W=.95, p > .05$) and personality clusters ABC ($W=.654, p < .05$).

Baseline Assessment

Test of normality of three scale SDS, BCI and IPDE at baseline period shows the results of the SDS as the data was not normally distributed so non-parametric test of Mann Whitney U test for two group comparison in which U value =77.0 at p value .13 (>.05). Table 1: Median, standard deviation and Mann Whitney U test of SDS for both experimental and control group at baseline period (N=30) so we accept null hypothesis that there was no difference in experimental and control group at baseline period on a scale of SDS. The rank difference of experimental group MR=17.8 while control group MR=13.1, med=26.5. for comparison of experimental and group on BCI. Homogeneity of variance was not violated as assessed by Levens' test for equality of variance assumed ($F=.42$). The control group ($M=45.1, sd=9.1$), experimental group ($M=41, sd=8.8$), the MD=4.86, 95% CI(1.87,11.60), $t(28) = 1.84, p = .51 (>.05)$. So it shows no differences on the brief cope inventory for both experimental and control group at baseline study.

Table 1

scale	Med(IQR)	Mean rank		Mann Whitney U	p
		Experimental Group (n=15)	Control Group (n=15)		
SDS	26.5(3.5)	17.8	13.1	77.0	.13

Outcomes

Table 2 :Mean, standard deviation and independent sample t test of SDS and BCI of both experimental and control group at post testing period shows the independent sample t test of experimental group $M=12.3 \pm 3.4$ and control group $M=12.3, \pm 3.9, t(28).145, p = .88 (< .05)$ and Cohen's $d = .04$ very small effect size of the variable at score of SDS. At BCI the control group $M=70, \pm 11.6$, experimental group $M=90, \pm 7.1, t(28) -5.8, p = .000 (< .05)$ with Cohen's $d = 2.0$ which shows the BCI were improved after therapeutic intervention. Results of two related sample of experimental group at baseline and end line period of score of SDS after intervention period of experimental group a reality therapy does improve individual's life domains at one of three levels ($z = -3.1, p = .001$). Median, mean rank and Wilcoxon signed ranked test at a baseline and end line period of experimental group of SDS. Indeed, median score at both pretest and posttest was $mdn=12.0$, showed high improvement in their disabilities domains of their life. BCI cut of scores at maladaptive range of experimental group at post period control $n=2$, experimental group $n=0$ while adaptive range at post testing period of control group $n=13$, experimental group $n=15$. Paired sample t test of scale of BCI at pretest of control group $M=45.8, 9.1 \pm$, posttest $M=70 \pm 11.6, t(14) -10.8, p < .000$ the results shows statistically significant difference between before and after pharmacological treatment and Cohen's $d = 2.3$ with $r = .68$.

Table # 2

Scales	Control group		Experimental group		$t(28)$	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
SDS	12.3	3.4	12.13	3.9	.145	.88	.04
BCI	70.0	11.6	90.9	7.1	-5.8	.000	2.07

Discussion:

This quasi-experimental study of clinical sample was to examine the coping abilities of the conversion patients before treatment intervention, results suggested that control group and experimental fall into maladaptive categories. After three months' intervention period of intervention (reality and behavior therapy) and

pharmacological treatment, the coping abilities score fall into adaptive range. Furthermore, there was significant difference between pre-test and post test period but no significant difference was found into the control and experimental group.

A study conducted in five teaching hospitals of Lahore (2013) by Ahmad & Bokhary, the independent sample t-test results, patients with conversion disorder used avoidance-focused coping strategies more frequently than patients with general medical conditions across all coping strategy categories. Furthermore, patients without conversion disorder used active focused coping techniques less frequently than patients with general medical conditions.

Asad, Saeed & Kausar (2016) conducted study on level of frustration and coping strategies by women of conversion disorder. The study consists of 50 women (25 conversion patients and 25 general medical condition women). The results showed conversion women had low frustration tolerance as compared to general medical condition. A significant difference was found between low frustration tolerance and avoidance focused coping among conversion patients as compared to general medical condition.

Binzer, Andersen, & Kullgren, (1997) conducted a study on a general group and conversion patients, the conversion group had a higher level of psychopathology, with 33% of the patients meeting the DSM-III-R axis I criteria for psychiatric syndromes and 50% having axis II personality disorders. Only 13% of conversion patients had dropped out of high school, compared to 67% of the control group, indicating a poor educational background. Conversion patients also reported significantly more traumatic life events prior to the onset of symptoms than controls. The current also indicated poor educational background of women with more traumatic life experiences as investigated by therapist while conducted combined therapy (reality and behavior therapy)

In 2017 Munir & Sarfraz correlational study, included 50 women with conversion disorder, aged between 12 and 60 years, with mean age of 24.4 (98%), 17 (34%) and 20 (40%) people belonged to the low socioeconomic class. Among women with conversion disorder, it was discovered that social inhibition, self-blame in non-adaptive ways, we also found that conversion women with low educational background coping abilities at non adaptive ways.

The current study investigated, conversion patients showed degree of impairments at three domains in life i.e. social life, family life and work/school life. Analysis of the results depicted, at baseline period both control and experimental group, all conversion patients were fell into categorize of markedly impaired in all three domains of their life at SDS score with mean rank of experimental group $MR=17.2$, control group $MR=13.7$ while median at 75 percentiles is 6 with mann Whitney $U=86.5$, $p=.19$ ($>.05$). While, the scores of both experimental and control group were improved after pharmacological and therapeutic intervention at endline period, the independent sample t test of experimental group $M=12.3 \pm 3.4$ and control group $M=12.3, \pm 3.9$, $t(28).145$ $p=.88$ ($<.05$) and Cohen's $d=.04$ very small effect size of the variable at score of SDS. Two related sample of experimental group at baseline and endline period of score of SDS after intervention period of experimental group a reality therapy does improve individual's life domains at one of three levels ($z=-3.1$, $p=.001$). Indeed, median score at both pretest and posttest was $mdn=12.0$ which depicts high improvement in their disabilities domains of their life. A study conducted in 2015 by Keertish & Sharma, adolescent's conversion patients had significant impairment in each of the domain i.e. interpersonal, school/work and self-fulfillment as compared to normal control group after treatment intervention. Morsy et al. (2022) conducted a meta-analysis on the relationship of life events and conversion disorder. Stressors that might alleviate the symptom were found to be relatively more frequent in patients than in pathological controls during family, relationship, and work events. Although it may support the idea that stressors play a different etiological role in the conversion disorder than they do in other disorders.

Liao et al. (2019) used multiple regression analysis score of SDS and QoL score fall into low quality of life and impairment in disabilities domains. The study showed comorbid condition of SDS with depression, similar to the current study, depression was high comorbidity psychological disorders compared to other psychiatric conditions.

Demartini et al. (2014) conducted a study in which comorbid mood disorder (primarily depression) affected 33% of the conversion patients, anxiety disorder affected 39%, and personality disorders affected 16% of patients. While in the current study Comorbid psychological disorder i.e. anxiety disorder (10%), depressive Disorder (80%), psychotic Disorder (3.3%) among the experimental and control group, at baseline period.

The current study examined personality disorders of conversion patients at baseline period of both experimental and control group data showed IPDE clusters of personality in which cluster B $n=2$ (6.7%), those who's score both in cluster A and B, $n=2$ (6.7%), those who falls in B and C, $n=20$ (66.7%) and those who's fall in A, B and C, $n=6$ (20%). which mean cluster B and C have high percentage of patients in which borderline personality were found more with cluster C dependent personality and compulsive personality disorder.

Henry et al. (2021) discuss the case of a young woman with high-risk self-injurious behavior who has been diagnosed with Emotionally Unstable Personality Disorder (EUPD). She also had functional neurological disorder, which showed up as immobility and nonepileptic seizures.

Søgaard, Mathiesen, & Simonsen, (2019) conducted a pilot study on patients with mixed sensory-motor functional neurological disorder. The patients were examined for differences in personality functioning, symptom severity, and personality pathology (conversion disorder). The study showed that severe personality functioning deficits were present in all patients. In order to develop a treatment plan, the study emphasized the clinical importance of determining personality functioning as part of an assessment on conversion patient's treatment.

Sar, Islam, & Öztürk, (2009) study found, conversion patients had borderline personality disorder. The only significant predictor of dissociation among the various types of childhood trauma was emotional abuse.

Schultze et al. (2012) said that Schizoid personality disorder was the best predictor of conversion, indicating more serious, long-lasting social deficits in later conversion disorder even at baseline. Given the close relationship between conversion disorder and personality.

In several large personality analyses, conversion symptoms were reported by about 40% of MPD patients (Bliss, 1984) These symptoms can be quite diverse and include paralysis, anesthesia, aphonia, blindness, and deafness (Taylor & Martin, 1944). In the course of illness, conversion symptoms typically appear briefly during a time of severe emotional distress. People with specific conversion symptoms are well-known personalities disorders.

Stone, Shapre & Binzer (2004) found that there is not much of a difference between patients with motor conversion symptoms and those who have pseudo seizures. Both individuals had significant emotional and personality disorders. The proportion of patients with borderline personality disorder was significantly higher in the group of patients who had pseudo seizures (35% vs. 7%).

The testing period of quasi experimental study i.e. Patients who received reality therapy and behavior therapy (progressive muscle relaxation technique) along with pharmacological treatment, showed improvement on BCI and Sheehan disability scale as compare to those in control group who received pharmacological treatment only. The results show high significant difference between before and after pharmacological treatment and Cohen's $d=2.3$ with $r=.68$.

Thus overall it was found both reality therapy, behavior therapy with pharmacological therapy improved the conversion patient's life domain at different perspectives and coping abilities were showed great improvement in both the groups. Reality therapy was the first line therapy approach in current study as earlier reality therapy was used for depression patients, behavioral problems Emotional problems and self-esteem and relationship problems. Therefore, given below are the compare and contrast of reality therapy and other treatment approaches for conversion patients in order to give accurate description of the study results.

Retraining and Control Therapy is a new cognitive behaviorally based intervention for pediatric functional neurological disorder (conversion) that is tested in a pilot randomized controlled trial (ReACT) by Fobian et al (2020). In this study participants were randomly assign 8 session of ReACT and supportive therapy. Control therapy resulted significant improvement of the conversion patients as compared to supportive therapy.

The study conducted by Reeder (2011) involved a difference in measures of (a) anxiety, (b) locus of control, (c) depression, and (d) self-esteem between a group of students who have been identified as having a behavioral or emotional disorder receiving choice therapy, 15 students from the experimental group who received the Choice Theory protocol and 15 students from the control group who did not received the Choice Theory protocol made up two random samples. The interaction suggests that after the Choice Theory (reality therapy) protocol was implemented, students in the experimental group reported feelings of greater improvement in depression, self-esteem and locus of control than did students in the control group who did not receive the treatment.

As compared to the current study, involved quasi experimental study of conversion patients but the reality therapy protocol of behavior self-evaluation, expectation vs reality and WDEP which are almost cover emotional and behavior problems of the patients when they experience high stress. Although there was no difference of experimental and control group after pretesting period but there was significant improvement of experimental groups in life disabilities scale and coping abilities of the conversion patients after therapeutic intervention.

Petra (2000) designed the study to evaluate the impact of a parenting program based on Choice theory and Reality therapy (RT/CT) on children's behavior. According to the findings, parenting education program and Reality therapy helped kids behave better at home and in school. In comparison to the above study the current study, has a sample of early adult female conversion patients and their behavior and emotional discomfort was treated through reality therapy. This study serves as another evidence for using reality therapy with conversion patients.

A 12-week semi-structured William Glasser reality/choice therapy group treatment intervention model was tested in the Gilliam (2004) to see if it was more efficient at treating people who commit domestic violence. The findings imply that the reality/choice therapy intervention model may have lessened the need for control over intimate partners in participants who had experienced domestic violence. Similar to the current study of conversion patients, assessing disabilities in life domains and therapeutic intervention of reality therapy.

Although the study is contrast, but providing efficient significance of using conversion patients of behavior problems, emotional aspects and reality versus expectation in the treatment intervention.

To address the new therapeutic intervention for conversion patients, additional research on randomized controlled trials in reality therapy is advised. This research should use data that enables observation of subtle patient's symptoms cues, provided to the therapist furthers strengthen different techniques of reality therapy.

Due to limited time and resources this study, has some inherent limitations. First of all, we collected clinical samples at designated hospitals only.so the sample size was small, thus cannot assure for the representativeness of the population.

It would have been helpful to validate our findings by comparing patients with conversion (functional neurological disorder) disorders to patients with other clinical disorders. this is a non-randomized study, so we cannot rule out the possibility of bias in the treatment selection, such as choosing women and those with one city of Pakistan only i.e. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa tertiary care hospitals. It did not consider the individual preferences and willingness to seek treatment in a quasi-experimental study.

Large-sample multi-center studies are required in the future. Given the excessively high medical costs and lost productivity associated with conversion disorder, future studies should examine the cost-effectiveness of various forms of psychotherapy. More high-quality randomized controlled studies should be included in future research due to the low quality of the body of existing studies. This would allow for more focused hypothesis testing of particular interventions and potential mechanisms of change, as well as comparisons between potentially effective psychotherapies for severe inpatients conversion disorder. Additionally, we have looked at the factors that affect prognosis, which include enhancing the bond and communication between their three domains in life i.e. social life, family life and work life to build trust and cooperation with them. All of these things will help the prognosis of these disorders.

Conversion disorder is a difficult mental illness that calls for a long-term commitment from the psychiatrist and utilizes the full range of psychiatric abilities. Conversion reactions are a somatic response to mental stability threats, which are typically attributed to an underlying mood disorder. The majority of the time, persistence through the diagnostic and treatment phases is rewarded by successful outcomes. To manage their mood disorders and related psychosocial issues, patients need long-term care. Making sure that any new physical symptom receives the proper medical investigation from the rest of the medical profession is one of the treating psychiatrist's key responsibilities.

Conclusion

This study generated the evidence that combined therapy (reality therapy and behavior therapy) are effective for the treatment of conversion in local setting of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This study found that outpatient's conversion disorder show degree of impairments in three domains of life i.e. social life, school and family life both experimental and control groups at baseline period. While after treatment intervention pharmacology of control group showed improvement in score of disability scale same as experimental group after treatment intervention of both pharmacological and therapy.

This study investigated personality disorders of conversion patients in both experimental and control group at baseline period. our results depicted the analysis that the most of personality fell on a cluster of B and C which indicates borderline personality, dependent and compulsive disorders. The study assessed the stress coping abilities both in adaptive and nonadaptive range at baseline period of experimental and control group and found that almost all patients were fell in non-adaptive range at baseline period. while after treatment intervention i.e. Experimental group received combined therapy (reality and behavior therapy) the stress coping abilities were improved same as control group whose received pharmacological treatment at a period of three months. The results also showed significant differences between baseline and endline period of both experimental and control group at scale of disabilities (SDS). Both pharmacological and therapy (reality and behavior) do effect the psychological improvement of conversion patients and it's the new innovation of reality therapy that has also promising results (but while abstractly profounding improvement) in life of diseased person (conversion disorder).

At the end, it is concluded that for conversion disorder, other therapeutic intervention can be considered and need further exploration in the empirical field to provide benefits to the patients.

References

- Aamir, S., Farooq, S., & Jahangir, S. F. (2011). A Comparison of Life Events in Depressive Illness and Dissociative (Conversion) Disorders. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 8(2). (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Ahmad, Q. A., & Bokharey, I. Z. (2013). Resilience and coping strategies in the patients with conversion disorder and general medical conditions: a comparative study. *Malaysian Journal of Psychiatry*, 22(1), 39-50. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Alper, K., Devinsky, O., Perrine, K., Luciano, D., Vazquez, B., Pacia, S., & Rhee, E. (1997). Dissociation in epilepsy and conversion nonepileptic seizures. *Epilepsia*, 38(9), 991-997. (n.d.).

- American Psychiatric Association (2000), *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 4th Edition, Text Revision*. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Asad, S., Saeed, S., & Kausar, R. (2016). Level of frustration tolerance and coping strategies used by women with conversion disorder vs those with general medical conditions. *JPPS*, 13(2), 35-8. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Binzer, M., & Eisemann, M. (1998). Childhood experiences and personality traits in patients with motor conversion symptoms. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 98(4), 288-295. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Bliss, EL. (1984). A symptom profile of patients with multiple personalities, including MMPI results. *Journal Of Nervous And Mental Disease*, 172, 197-202. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Bradley, S., & Taylor, J. (2004). Ethnicity, educational attainment and the transition from school. *The Manchester School*, 72(3), 317-346. (n.d.).
- Brown, R. J., & Ron, M. A. (2002). Conversion and somatoform disorders. In *Encyclopedia of the human brain*. Academic Press, Ltd. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Campo, J. V., & Negrini, B. J. (2000). Case study: Negative reinforcement and behavioral management of conversion disorder. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 39(6), 787-790. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Carver, C. S., Scheier, M. F., & Weintraub, J. K. (1989). Assessing coping strategies: a theoretically based approach. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 56(2), 267. (n.d.).
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education*, 6. Baskı, Oxon: Routledge. (n.d.).
- Coles, J. L., Daniel, N. D., & Naveen, L. (2014). Co-opted boards. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 27(6), 1751-1796. (n.d.).
- Demartini, B., Batla, A., Petrochilos, P., Fisher, L., Edwards, M. J., & Joyce, E. (2014). Multidisciplinary treatment for functional neurological symptoms: a prospective study. *Journal of Neurology*, 261, 2370-2377. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Dias, C., Cruz, J. F., & Fonseca, A. M. (2012). The relationship between multidimensional competitive anxiety, cognitive threat appraisal, and coping strategies: A multi-sport study. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 10(1), 52-65. ed. (n.d.).
- Eysenck, H. J. (1959). Learning theory and behaviour therapy. *Journal of Mental Science*, 105(438), 61-75. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Farooq, S. (2007). Conversion disorder-A dilemma facing the psychiatrist in developing countries. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 4(1), 60-2. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Farooq, S. (2007). Conversion disorder-A dilemma facing the psychiatrist in developing countries. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 4(1), 60-2. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Fobian, A. D., Long, D. M., & Szaflarski, J. P. (2020). Retraining and control therapy for pediatric psychogenic non-epileptic seizures. *Annals of Clinical and Translational Neurology*, 7(8), 1410-1419. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Folkman, S., & Lazarus, R. S. (1980). An analysis of coping in a middle-aged community sample. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 219-239. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Freud, S. ((1962).). On the grounds for detaching a particular syndrome from neurasthenia under the description 'anxiety neurosis'. In *The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud, Volume III (1893-1899): Early Psycho-Analytic Pu*.
- Freud, s. (1962b). (1962). Freud, S. (1962). Further remarks on the neuro-psychoses of defense. In *The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud, Volume III (1893-1899): Early Psycho-Analytic Publications* (pp. 157-185).
- Gall, M. D., Borg, W. R., & Gall, J. P. (1996). *Educational research: An introduction*. Longman Publishing. (n.d.).
- Gilliam, A. (2004). *The efficacy of William Glasser reality/choice theory with domestic violence perpetrators: A treatment outcome study* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University). (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Gumà-Uriel, L., Peñarrubia-María, M. T., Cerdà-Lafont, M., Cunillera-Puertolas, O., Almeda-Ortega, J., Fernández-Vergel, R., ... & Luciano, J. V. (2016). Impact of IPDE-SQ personality disorders on the healthcare and societal costs of fibromyalgia patients. (n.d.).
- Henry, J., Collins, E., Griffin, A., & Zimbron, J. (2021). Treatment of severe emotionally unstable personality disorder with comorbid Ehlers-Danlos syndrome and functional neurological disorder in an inpatient setting: a case for specialist units without. (n.d.).
- International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (11th ed.; ICD-11; World Health Organization, 2019). (n.d.).
- Keertish, N., & Sharma, I. (2015). Impairment and classroom environment in adolescents with conversion disorder. *Journal of Indian Association for Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 11(2), 99-120. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Kroenke, K., & Swindle, R. (2000). *Cognitive behavioural therapy for somatisation and*. (n.d.). (n.d.).

- Liao, S. C., Ma, H. M., Lin, Y. L., & Huang, W. L. (2019). Functioning and quality of life in patients with somatic symptom disorder: the association with comorbid depression. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 90, 88-94. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Munir, H. A., & Sarfraz, N. (2021). Interpersonal problems, optimism and coping styles among women with conversion disorder: A correlational study. *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 71(12), 2717-2720. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Nicholson, T. R. J., & Kanaan, R. A. A. (2009). Conversion disorder. *Psychiatry*, 8(5), 164–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mppsy.2009.03.001>. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Petra, J. R. (2000). The effects of a choice theory and reality therapy parenting program on children's behavior. The Union Institute. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Reeder, S. D. (2011). Choice theory: An investigation of the treatment effects of a choice theory protocol on students identified as having a behavioral or emotional disability on measures of anxiety, depression, locus of control and self-esteem (Doctoral. (n.d.).
- Şar, V., Akyüz, G., Kundakçı, T., Kızıltan, E., & Doğan, O. (2004). Childhood trauma, dissociation, and psychiatric comorbidity in patients with conversion disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 161(12), 2271-2276. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Schultze-Lutter, F., Klosterkötter, J., Michel, C., Winkler, K., & Ruhrmann, S. (2012). Personality disorders and accentuations in at-risk persons with and without conversion to first-episode psychosis. *Early intervention in psychiatry*, 6(4), 389-398. (n. (n.d.).
- Sheehan, D. V., Claycomb, J. B., & Kouretas, N. (1981). Monoamine oxidase inhibitors: prescription and patient management. *The International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine*, 10(2), 99-121. (n.d.).
- Søgaard, U., Mathiesen, B. B., & Simonsen, E. (2019). Personality and psychopathology in patients with mixed sensory-motor functional neurological disorder (conversion disorder): a pilot study. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 207(7), 546-554. (. (n.d.).
- Stone, J., Carson, A., & Sharpe, M. (2005a). Functional symptoms and signs of neurology:. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Taylor, W.S. & Martin, M.F. (1944) Multiple personality. *Journal Of Abnormal And Social Psychology*, 39, 281-300. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Thompson, M. E. et al. (2012). *Child and adolescent mental health: Theory and practice*. Hodder Arnold. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Vyas, J. N., & Bharadwaj, P. K. (1977). A study of hysteria—An analysis of 304 patients. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 19(4), 71-74. (n.d.). (n.d.).
- Wubbolding, R. E. (2000). *Reality therapy for the 21st century*. Brunner-Routledge. (n.d.). (n.d.).

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